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Improving the Pupil's Reading Comprehension Using PQ4R and Annotations: Instructional Tool

Mary Grace M. Mahusay,* BB. Rose O. Aguillon, Nino T. Baga, Mariz Bahenting, Cherry Lou L. Calabroso, Melody A. Canoy, Jeziel A. Dionaldo, Lezel Gabunada, Jan Michelle Guimaras, Khym Yvette A. Javierto, Jemelyn L. Morales, Kin Louie M. Patiluna, Marichie T. Sadagnet, Kyla Janin D. Sevilla, Laarnie Blessful M. Sucal, Joan Marie P. Tagyamon, Cyril A. Cabello, Vicente S. Erojo, Sulpicio D. Bani Jr., Ana Marie R. Schauf

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study explored the pupil's reading comprehension using the Preview, Question, Read, Reflect, Recite, and Review (PQ4R) and Annotations as a basis for an instructional tool. Grade six learners are struggling with reading comprehension, especially during the pandemic. It is pivotal that educational strategy and technique should be tested and explored to address the gap. This study used the PQ4R and annotations to help the learners understand the concepts and subject matter. This study utilized a sequential explanatory mixed-method research design. This design followed a sequence of gathering data from quantitative for analysis and interpretation to qualitative for exploration and triangulation. For the specific design of this method, a Quasi-experimental will be used to understand the numerical value of this study and a descriptive qualitative for the qualitative data. Purposive sampling design will be used in this study following criteria to identify the prospected respondents. There were 30 respondents from Tuble Elementary School. This study utilized a validated instrument. The findings of the study stipulated that the results of the experimental group (p -value = 0.28) and the control group (p -value = 0.34) established no significant difference. With this, teachers must explore more strategies and techniques in education so that learners can get the best learning experiences that they deserve. This will provide a reference on how teachers can create instructional tools to increase classroom productivity.

Keywords: *reading comprehension, PQ4R, quasi-experimental, descriptive qualitative, instructional tool*

Introduction

Poor reading comprehension is currently a significant concern for teachers, and this concern has persisted for many years. Most learners can accurately read but frequently struggle to comprehend the meaning of the text they are reading. Additionally, this issue worsened after the COVID-19 pandemic when learners ceased attending school physically and received limited instruction in reading. As a result, learners struggle to improve their problem-solving skills and receive low scores in written examinations, as evidenced by the 2022 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), where the Philippines ranked 76th out of 81 countries globally. Due to a significant correlation between reading comprehension and problem-solving skills, reading comprehension affects pupils' academic performance and problem-solving abilities as a contributory factor (Jala, 2020). In response to these challenges, teachers have been adapting and developing various strategies over time, and this study delves into assessing the effectiveness of PQ4R and annotations as instructional tools in elevating reading comprehension among learners.

According to Khasawneh (2020), reading is a complex cognitive activity wherein individuals interpret written symbols, comprehend the meaning conveyed, and mentally convert these symbols into verbal representations, facilitating a comprehensive understanding of the written text. Nevertheless, it requires an intensive focus where teachers should incorporate innovative approaches because teaching reading comprehension poses challenges. Despite the prolonged research efforts, the reading comprehension levels of U.S. adolescents, as reflected in national and international scores show minimal improvement, revealing a noticeable lack of substantial progress in how well adolescents understand what they read on both national and global scales. Thus, diverse theoretical frameworks that provide various lenses require highlighted focus.

Additionally, it necessitates a collaborative effort among teachers, researchers, and policymakers to improve the overall quality of instruction necessary for heightening the level of reading comprehension among adolescents (Elleman & Oslund, 2019). Much like in the Philippines, students grapple with difficulties in reading comprehension, vocabulary acquisition, and critical thinking skills, ultimately impacting their overall academic proficiency. However, there are recognized areas for enhancement that can be made through advocating initiatives to foster early literacy, allocating resources to enhance teacher training, and crafting reading materials for Filipino learners (Cabello et al., 2021). These efforts have been emphasized as the pilot in shaping the educational policies and methodologies in the Philippines dedicated to advancing the reading abilities of Filipino students (Idulog et al., 2023).

Myriad studies, including Jala (2020) and Torppa et al. (2020), proved the significant impact of reading comprehension on academic performance across various subjects and grade levels. However, improving pupils' reading comprehension poses challenges including but not limited to reading fluency, coupled with issues related to motivation and overall well-being. Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic also took part in exacerbating the case in the realm of reading comprehension (Ando et al., 2022; Villar et al., 2022). With the abrupt shift to remote learning and the disruption of traditional classroom environments, many students have struggled to maintain

their reading skills, hindered by the lack of face-to-face instruction and limited access to resources (Jaicten et al., 2023). To promote equitable learning opportunities and ensure academic success in the post-pandemic era, teachers are encouraged to employ various methods (Cariaga et al., 2022; Ugbamen et al., 2022) and strategies (Enario et al., 2022; Pulgo et al., 2022). One of these is the PQ4R and Annotation. By incorporating the PQ4R method and annotations into their reading practice, students develop a systematic approach to comprehension, addressing challenges posed by lack of reading comprehension and fostering active engagement, critical thinking, and deeper understanding, ultimately leading to improved academic performance (Rahmadia & Fatimah, 2021).

In this study, the researchers propose implementing the PQ4R method alongside annotations as the independent variable to enhance the reading comprehension of students experiencing academic challenges. The PQ4R method, comprising Preview, Question, Read, Reflect, Recite, and Review, offers a structured framework aimed at optimizing comprehension. Previewing allows students to familiarize themselves with the text's structure and content, activating prior knowledge and setting expectations. Subsequently, questioning prompts active engagement and purposeful reading, fostering deeper understanding. Annotations during reading serve as valuable tools for tracking comprehension and identifying key information. Post-reading activities such as reflection and recitation further reinforce learning and ensure accuracy (Ancot et al., 2023). The dependent variable of this study is the improvement in academic performance, potentially resulting from the integration of the PQ4R method and annotations. This research aims to explore the efficacy of this approach in addressing reading comprehension challenges among students.

Amidst this emerging concern in the academe, the continuous evolution of myriad strategies signifies a dynamic and ever-changing landscape of diverse approaches unfolding over time (Gabriel et al., 2022). Various strategies have been formed, nevertheless, they converge toward a common objective- to overcome the challenge and turn it into a historical chapter. Hence, this study delves into proving that PQ4R and Annotations can be a powerful duo for effective teaching, offering a structured approach to enhance understanding and retention among learners. It underscores the importance of equipping educators with the knowledge and skills to effectively implement PQ4R and annotations to ensure an impactful application of these strategies in diverse educational settings. Additionally, this research accentuates the potential variations of the effectiveness of PQ4R and annotations. Understanding these instructional strategies can optimize learners' comprehension, resulting in augmented academic performance.

Research Questions

This study explored the reading comprehension of the Grade 6 pupils using PQ4R and Annotations in Tuble Elementary School for the school year 2023-2024 as a basis for an instructional tool. Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What are the pre-test and post-test scores of the control and experimental group?
2. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the control and experimental groups?
3. What are the learning experiences of the respondents and the teachers in utilizing the instructional intervention?

Literature Review

Initiating instructional efforts early is crucial for developing comprehension skills (Duke et al., 2021). Despite the importance of comprehension, educators continue to grapple with the challenge of poor reading comprehension, affecting learners' ability to grasp written content and impeding academic performance. Therefore, teachers must utilize effective instructional tools in teaching reading comprehension, enabling them to assist learners in overcoming challenges in understanding the text (Nurdianingsih, 2021). This literature review delves into the effectiveness of integrating PQ4R and annotation strategies among learners, empowering them to approach reading as an active process and enhancing comprehension skills for a more effective and personalized learning experience. The incorporation of these instructional tools into teaching practices not only cultivates a deeper understanding of the content but also fosters increased student engagement throughout the reading process (Segarino et al., 2022). Thus, the scrutinized articles contribute to enriching the ongoing study and provide a framework that facilitates understanding of its significance.

PQ4R has been identified as a method to enhance memory and awareness in students' learning processes, integrating self-planning, self-monitoring, and self-evaluation within its steps: Preview, Question, Read, Reflect, Recite, and Review. Ariyani (2023) modified the strategy by incorporating a summary activity, aimed at improving reading comprehension. This addition involves students summarizing the reading results in their own words during the review stage, thereby facilitating a deeper understanding of the material. Consequently, the researcher in this study seeks to compare the effectiveness of PQ4R with and without the summary activity, aiming to ascertain its impact on student achievement.

Fitriani and Suhardi (2019) underscored the pivotal role of teachers in advancing students' reading comprehension through the adoption of effective pedagogical methods. Among these methods, the PQ4R learning model emerged as a prominent strategy, comprising Preview, Question, Read, Reflect, Recite, and Review stages. This model fosters systematic learning and actively engages students in their educational journey, thereby fostering the enhancement of reading skills, writing proficiency, and memory retention. The primary objective of their study is to delineate the implementation of the PQ4R model and underscore its significance in bolstering reading comprehension abilities. Drawing upon a comprehensive review of literature spanning various sources, the researchers have elucidated the efficacy of the PQ4R learning model in augmenting students' reading comprehension. Such findings advocate for the widespread adoption and dissemination of the PQ4R model within educational contexts, ensuring that students can harness the benefits of this

structured and interactive learning approach.

In advocating for the integration of comprehension instruction within educational frameworks, Duke et al. (2021) underscore the importance of a systematic approach to recognizing, understanding, and critically evaluating textual content. Their argument extends beyond the notion that comprehension involves mere reading and memorization; instead, it emphasizes the ability to derive meaning from text, summarize effectively, draw informed conclusions, and apply acquired knowledge. Contrary to the belief that reading fluency alone ensures comprehensive understanding, the authors stress the necessity of explicit instruction, advocating for the implementation of strategies like PQ4R to bolster students' reading comprehension skills. Furthermore, Duke et al. highlight the significance of expanding vocabulary based on students' existing knowledge, to deepen understanding and engagement with textual material. The importance of aligning reading materials with students' interests to enhance motivation and foster the development of personal goals, perspectives, and values. The proposed instructional model is characterized as a multifaceted approach, advocating for the incorporation of diverse materials and methodologies to enrich and cultivate students' reading comprehension abilities, thereby offering valuable insights for educators seeking to optimize literacy instruction.

In their investigation into the impact of the PQ4R strategy on fourth-grade students' reading comprehension skills, Yacoub and Hussein (2024) demonstrated the potential effectiveness of PQ4R as an instructional tool for enhancing reading abilities in this age group. Their study provides valuable insights for educators and researchers seeking to improve reading instruction practices. By promoting students' engagement through the expression of opinions, exploration of ideas, questioning, and active participation in lessons, the PQ4R method facilitated positive interactions, highlighting its efficacy. The findings underscore the importance of prioritizing reading comprehension and incorporating modern teaching strategies, such as PQ4R, into Arabic Language instruction, offering implications for curriculum development and pedagogical approaches in language education. Additionally, their study emphasizes the need for continued exploration and refinement of instructional methods to meet the diverse needs of learners.

The PQ4R method, as highlighted by Tyastuti (2019), holds significance in education by effectively improving reading comprehension skills. This structured approach, Preview, Question, Read, Reflect, Recite, and Review, enhances students' ability to understand, retain, and vocabulary recognition during reading activities. The PQ4R method was assessed for its effectiveness in enhancing comprehension of narrative texts among first-grade senior high school students. The result suggested that the PQ4R method is an effective instructional strategy for teaching reading comprehension to first-grade senior high school students. The objective of PQ4R as a learning method is to support learners in comprehending concepts by engaging in planning, monitoring, and evaluating their learning stages. This approach utilizes the writing process as a tool to study and understand reading texts, facilitating a more active and effective learning experience and providing valuable insights for educators and researchers seeking to enhance literacy instruction practice (Dzulhikam & Dewi, 2020).

Fatimah (2021) hypothesized before a systematic study that the PQ4R strategy does not affect improving reading comprehension, and also indicating that the PQ4R strategy does indeed enhance students' reading comprehension. However, the former hypothesis was rejected while the latter was embraced in the study. This acceptance of the latter hypothesis underscores the meaningful impact of implementing the PQ4R strategy in supporting students' proficiency in understanding written content. These findings provide valuable insights into the efficacy of PQ4R strategy. With the dual emphasis on rejection and acceptance of hypotheses, substantially this contributes to the ongoing discourse on evidence-based approaches to elevate students' reading comprehension skills, offering significant implications for educational practice and research. By acknowledging the effectiveness of PQ4R, significant implications for educational practice and research where educators can tailor their teaching approaches to augment students' reading comprehension abilities have been shed light.

Anggraeni (2020) conducted a study to explore the effectiveness of the PQ4R strategy in enhancing students' comprehension of narrative reading texts within a classroom setting. Employing a descriptive qualitative research design, data was collected through observation and field notes during three reading sessions: before, during, and after reading. The pre-reading phase primarily focused on the preview and question stages of PQ4R, while the post-reading phase utilized the review stage to assess comprehension. The during-reading sessions incorporated the remaining stages of the PQ4R method. The study findings underscored the significance of the PQ4R strategy in improving students' understanding of narrative texts, highlighting its potential value for educators in enhancing reading comprehension skills among students.

Shodieva (2023) emphasizes the pivotal role of summarization in academic writing, highlighting its ability to succinctly convey the main ideas, arguments, and points. Summarization is a process that requires analytical thinking, comprehension, and the extraction of essential concepts, fostering critical thought and aiding in the understanding of a text's central ideas. Effective summary writing hinges on a comprehensive understanding of the original content and the adept evaluation of key ideas, details, and underlying arguments. Annotating crucial passages, such as topic sentences, assists in pinpointing primary concepts and pertinent details within the text. Moreover, it facilitates improved writing and communication skills by identifying important elements within a text, including both overt and covert information. A well-crafted summary goes beyond mere condensation, presenting a clear and concise representation of the text's main ideas. In the academic context, the researcher underscores the critical importance of summarization for succinctly communicating main ideas, arguments, and points, requiring proficiency in critical thinking and the ability to identify and highlight key concepts from source materials.

In their comprehensive study, Smith et al. (2022) delve into the intricate dynamics of background knowledge and its impact on the reading comprehension abilities of primary school children, particularly those in mid to late primary grades. Categorizing learners into two distinct groups—stronger and weaker readers—the study elucidates how varying levels of background knowledge influence reading outcomes differently. While learners with lower background knowledge may benefit from well-connected texts, weaker readers often exhibit improvement when exposed to ample background knowledge. The research underscores the necessity for educators to consider these nuanced effects when designing instructional reading materials and strategies to ensure fairness and inclusivity in learning. Through an exhaustive examination of twenty-three relevant studies, the authors unravel the complexities of the relationship between background knowledge and reading comprehension abilities, shedding light on its multifaceted nature. Furthermore, the study advocates for the exploration of interventions aimed at enriching students' background knowledge, which could significantly enhance comprehension and provide valuable insights for educators seeking to optimize literacy instruction.

In their study, Azmuddim et al. (2020) underscore the significance of annotations in enhancing learners' comprehension of academic material, particularly in subjects like Science and Technology. The research emphasizes the effectiveness of guiding students in annotation techniques as a successful approach to promoting reading comprehension. By providing students with annotation tools, the study reveals notable advancements in their understanding of the subject matter, as these tools facilitate active interaction and allow students to mark and note crucial information. The findings suggest that engagement through annotations contributes to a deeper comprehension of academic content. The integration of annotation tools is viewed as essential for achieving favorable learning outcomes, fostering a dynamic exchange between students and the material. This interactive approach aligns with contemporary educational strategies, creating a more engaging and collaborative learning environment that ultimately enhances the overall learning experience for students.

The diverse range of literature gathered above underscores the significance of understanding how research is carried out. It compiles various studies on the PQ4R strategy and Annotations, summarizing their importance and effectiveness in enhancing reading comprehension. Through pre-test and post-test evaluations, the study demonstrates the value of these strategies and their potential as tools for future researchers to explore further in the realm of reading comprehension. This research serves as a foundation for identifying effective strategies that can aid learners in enhancing their reading comprehension skills.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a sequential explanatory mixed-method research design. This design followed a sequence of gathering data from quantitative for analysis and interpretation to qualitative for exploration and triangulation. For the specific design of this method, a Quasi-experimental will be used to understand the numerical value of this study and a descriptive qualitative for the qualitative data. These designs are essential in sustaining the rigor, validity, and reliability of the study where the researchers capitalize on the strength of these designs establishing a more robust understanding of the gap of the study which is the reading comprehension of the learners.

Participants

Purposive sampling design will be used in this study following criteria to identify the prospected respondents. There were 30 respondents from Tuble Elementary School. They were selected as respondents because they are being challenged in terms of reading comprehension. This study will be conducted in Barangay Tuble, Moalboal for the School Year 2023-2024 as a basis for making instructional tools.

Instruments

This study utilized a researcher-made instrument. The quantitative instrument which is a multiple-choice question and the qualitative instrument which is a semi-structured questionnaire went through different phases of validation and reliability testing such as face, criterion, content, and construct, as discussed by Colton and Covert (2007) cited by Cabello and Bonotan (2021). There are 20 items elicited from the teacher, who is also one of the co-authors of this study, handling the class for the quantitative instrument. 3 questions were structured to know the experiences of the teacher in handling the class using the intervention. The items were screened by the researchers to see if the items were in line with how reading comprehension is gauged. After this, the instrument was sent to three experts in the field of education primarily an expert teaching reading for more than 10 years. One of the experts has a background in Instrument validation such as a Doctor of Philosophy major in Research and Evaluation. Lastly, an expert in Psychology whose expertise is in measuring the other factors affecting how a child reads and learns in reading validated the instrument. With these steps, the instrument was concluded as valid and reliable.

Procedure

The researchers crafted a letter to ask permission to gather the data. After its approval, the researchers set a schedule to conduct the study. The identified groups of respondents were known after a quick evaluation of their reading comprehension skills. To sustain impartiality, the researchers made sure to divide the class accordingly. The control group is composed of readers from different levels and will utilize the traditional way of learning reading comprehension while the experimental group which consists of readers in

different levels as well will experience the intervention which is PQ4R and Annotations. Before the start of data gathering, the researchers secured an Assent Form and Consent Form from the parents of the learners and the teacher to protect the rights of the respondents that at any time, they can leave, and they will not be forced to complete the study because this is purely voluntary without any compensation. Their information will be treated with the highest degree of confidentiality as part of the ethical consideration that this study upholds (Bell & Bryman, 2007). The data gathered will then be treated and analyzed according to what is identified in this study.

Data Analysis

In treating and analyzing the quantitative data, mean and standard deviation will be used in presenting the pretest and post-test scores of the groups of respondents, and in establishing the significant difference in the pretest and post-test scores of the groups of respondents, the T-test will be utilized.

In analyzing the qualitative data, Braun and Clarke's Analysis will be used following the steps in identifying themes and subthemes of the participant's experiences.

Results and Discussion

The tables below contain detailed explanations of the discussions and interpretations related to the analysis, addressing the research questions.

Table 1. *The Pre-test and Post-test scores of the Experimental Group*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Pre-test</i>	<i>Post-test</i>
1	2	0
2	1	1
3	4	4
4	4	3
5	2	3
6	1	0
7	5	6
8	2	4
9	4	4
10	1	3
11	4	4
12	2	2
13	3	3
14	2	5
15	5	5
Mean:	2.8	3.13
SD:	1.37	1.70

Table 1 shows the pre-test and post-test scores of the Experimental Group. It can be gleaned that the average score on the pre-test is 2.8 and the post-test score is 3.13. In the pre-test score, the highest score was garnered by respondent 7, which was 5; in the post-test result, respondent 7 gained the highest score, which was 6. This implies that with the scores and its difference, the intervention which is the PQ4R, and Annotation is effective and was well taken by the experimental group of respondents. With this, the intervention can be proposed to increase the level of comprehension among those learners who are having difficulty in reading.

According to Orellana et al. (2024), strong reading comprehension skills are crucial for comprehending and engaging with academic content, directly influencing a student's performance across various subjects. Students with higher reading proficiency often achieve better grades and demonstrate greater overall academic success compared to their peers who struggle with reading (Abid et al., 2023). As facilitators of learning, teachers must seek interventions to assist students in enhancing their reading and comprehension abilities as essential lifelong skills (Nurdianingsih, 2021). PQ4R emerges as a valuable method for promoting student engagement and allowing educators to discern notable differences in students' reading comprehension levels, particularly when coupled with effective annotation techniques (Fitriani et al., 2019). This approach, which encourages students to preview, question, read, reflect, recite, and review texts while actively annotating key points and insights, potentially paves the way for future academic endeavors as students embrace its purpose in enhancing their reading comprehension.

Table 2 shows the pre-test and post-test scores of the control group. The average pre-test score is 2.4, while the post-test score is 2.6. Notably, respondent 11 achieved the highest pre-test score of 5, whereas respondents 1, 2, and 8 obtained the highest post-test score of 4. Based on the scores and their differences, it is evident that there is minimal progress occurred. Compared to the experimental group, the progress in the control group is quite lower which signifies that there should be an intervention of the PQ4R and annotation during the reading session to improve reading comprehension.

Butterfuss et al. (2020) propose a comprehensive framework for understanding reading, emphasizing three interconnected components:

the reader, the text, and the activity all with a broader sociocultural context. Effective reading comprehension involves navigating not only individual texts but also the multifaceted nature of the information. Additionally, the study of Rahmadia and Fatimah (2020) discusses teaching methods, student motivation, and reading skills, showing how elements are interconnected in education. This prompts reflection on how teachers can make learning engaging for diverse students and emphasizes the importance of understanding students' motivation for learning. It also focuses on how vital recognizing the diverse backgrounds and experiences that readers bring to their engagement with texts, highlighting how these factors shape interpretation and comprehension as stated in the study of Butterfuss et al., 2020. In general, it emphasizes the intricate nature of the educational process and the persistent search for better strategies to aid student learning.

Table 2. *The pre-test and post-test scores of the Control Group*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Pre-test</i>	<i>Post-test</i>
1	3	4
2	4	4
3	0	2
4	0	2
5	4	3
6	2	1
7	2	3
8	4	4
9	3	2
10	1	0
11	5	2
12	3	3
13	1	3
14	2	3
15	2	3
Mean:	2.4	2.6
SD:	1.45	1.05

Table 3 shows the differences in pre-test and post-test results between the control and experimental groups. The sample size for both groups is the same (n=15). However, the tested level of significance for both groups is 0.05, indicating that there is no significant difference between them. This suggests that during the utilization of PQ4R, there were factors that affected the strategies for effective reading comprehension among the students.

Table 3. *Pre-test and Post-test Difference between Controlled and Experimental Groups*

<i>Groups</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Alpha</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Experimental	15	14	-0.56875	0.28703	0.05	Not significant	Accept the null hypotheses
Controlled	15	14	-0.4132	0.341305	0.05	Not significant	Accept the null hypotheses

PQ4R is a learning strategy used by teachers to improve learners' reading comprehension. However, according to Holt (2023), effective PQ4R implementation may take some practice and adaptation. The transition to this structured approach may be difficult initially, as students will be adapting to the strategy and may need time to adjust.

Table 4. *The Qualitative Analysis*

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Sub-Themes</i>	<i>Authentic Experiences</i>
Milestones	Improvement in comprehension.	“The reading intervention went really well! For instance, few students who struggled with comprehension showed significant improvement after the said intervention. Before, they would stumble over multisyllabic words and lose track of the main idea.”
Scarcities	Poor reading: Poor comprehension Teachers' significant role Implicit and explicit comprehension	“Students who have a difficulty in reading have the higher instance not to understand the reading passage(s) given by the teacher-moderator. So the teacher needs to find way(s) specifically an intervention in order to cater the problem of the certain students. Yes, it improved students' comprehension in reading between and behind the lines on the certain passage(s).”
Challenges	Environmental Challenges to Intervention	“Yes, as mentioned above like noise, heat index. and other distractions are hindrances to conduct the interventions. They can lose focus due to noise given by the surroundings and also the higher heat index we felt gives a more difficult scenario in administering the intervention.”
Enhancement	Peer Tutoring Extended implementation	“I suggest to give more focus specifically in peer tutoring which it gives better impact to the child's comprehension and ability to read. Aside from that, it should be taught for longer periods like weeks or months.”

There are four emerging themes about the lived experiences of the teacher. These are the Milestones, The Scarcities, The Enhancement, and The Challenges. These themes are comprehensively discussed in the literature below.

Theme 1: Milestones

The success of the intervention in improving students' reading comprehension is evident through the notable improvement observed among those who were initially struggling. The intervention effectively benefited these students, leading to enhanced reading comprehension skills (Zuriah, 2020). This positive outcome underscores the effectiveness of the intervention in addressing the specific needs of struggling students and facilitating their progress in mastering reading. The significant improvement in reading comprehension is a clear indicator of the success of the intervention in promoting academic growth and fostering a supportive learning environment for all students.

The Teacher said that:

“The reading intervention went really well! For instance, few students who struggled with comprehension showed significant improvement after the said intervention. Before, they would stumble over multisyllabic words and lose track of the main idea.”

The teacher highlighted the significance of integrating PQ4R and Annotations to enhance students' comprehension. The intervention was essential and effective as it enabled students to take significant steps forward in understanding the material they read, marking a notable improvement in their reading comprehension skills.

Theme 2: The Scarcities

Interventions cover a range of crucial components. Filderman et al. (2021) delve into the comparative impacts of different strategies to improve comprehension among struggling readers. This highlights the crucial need to address these specific challenges head-on in comprehension intervention efforts. The teacher plays a crucial role in identifying students who are struggling and delivering effective instruction based on established practices. These practices often include providing explicit instruction in comprehension strategies such as predicting, questioning, and summarizing, while also incorporating visual aids for improved understanding. Furthermore, interventions should encourage the development of both implicit and explicit comprehension skills, guiding students in consciously applying strategies while also nurturing their unconscious use of context clues and prior knowledge. According to Gersten et al. (2020), the study evaluates how effective reading interventions are in various aspects such as word and pseudoword reading, reading comprehension, and passage fluency. It also investigates how different intervention and study variables influence the outcomes for students who are at risk for reading difficulties. Intervention should be multifaceted, addressing the specific needs of individual students while recognizing support and effective instruction. Interventions can help students become more proficient readers who are better able to understand and engage with a wide range of texts.

A participant stated that,

“Students who have difficulty in reading have the higher instance not to understand the reading passage(s) given by the teacher-moderator. So, the teacher needs to find way(s) specifically an intervention to cater the problem of the certain students.”

The participant highlights students with reading difficulties often face the common challenge of struggling to understand the reading passages provided by their teacher. This is a crucial issue because comprehension is essential for literacy development and academic success in all subjects. It also highlights the teacher's responsibility to address this issue. Identifying specific challenges and implementing effective interventions is a critical role that teachers play in supporting struggling readers. The interventions may differ based on the nature and severity of the reading difficulties. It also indicates the necessity of proactive measures to meet the needs of struggling students. Rather than simply acknowledging the problem, the teacher-moderator must actively seek out ways to support these students in improving their reading comprehension skills. This may involve ongoing assessment, collaboration with specialists, and the implementation of evidence-based strategies within the classroom environment.

A participant mentioned that,

“Yes, it improved students' comprehension in reading between and behind the lines on the certain passage(s).”

The participant indicates an improvement in students' understanding skills has been observed due to a specific intervention or approach, particularly in their capacity to comprehend not only the explicit meaning of the text but also the implied messages within a given passage. The positive result of the intervention is evident in terms of comprehension, allowing students to grasp the deeper meanings and themes of texts. The reference to comprehending "between and behind the lines" indicates that students are not solely comprehending the literal content of the passage but also drawing inferences about implicit meanings, underlying themes, and authorial intent. This signifies a higher level of reading comprehension, enabling students to analyze text beyond its surface level and explore its complexities. This reflects a positive outcome in terms of students' comprehension abilities, particularly in their capacity to discern meaning both explicitly stated and implied within given passages. This development is indicative of effective teaching practices and interventions aimed at fostering deeper levels of understanding and critical engagement with texts.

Theme 3: The Challenges

Indeed, challenges such as noise, high heat index, and other distractions can impede the successful execution of interventions. It underscores several aspects of students' vulnerability to heat exposure and its adverse impact on their health, such as absence from

school, and physical symptoms of heat distress (Lala & Hagishima, 2023). The surrounding noise can disrupt concentration, leading to a loss of focus among students during intervention activities. Additionally, elevated heat levels can create a more challenging environment for implementing interventions effectively. Overcoming these obstacles is essential to ensure that interventions are carried out smoothly and meet the needs of students. Strategies must be adapted to mitigate the impact of these challenges and create a conducive setting for data gathering and intervention implementation.

Participant mentioned that,

"Yes, as mentioned above like noise, heat index, and other distractions are hindrances to conduct the interventions. They can lose focus due to noise given by the surroundings and also the higher heat index we felt gives a more difficult scenario in administering the intervention."

The participant highlighted those distractions such as noise, heat index, and other factors can impede the effectiveness of interventions. He expressed concern about the potential loss of focus among participants due to surrounding noise and the challenges posed by high heat index levels during intervention administration. The participant emphasized the negative impact of these distractions on creating a conducive environment for interventions. He acknowledged that noise and heat could make it more difficult to carry out interventions successfully. The participant's insight underscores the importance of addressing external distractions to ensure that interventions are conducted smoothly and that participants can engage fully in the process. By recognizing and mitigating these hindrances, the participant emphasized the need to optimize the intervention environment for better outcomes. Managing noise disturbances and heat levels was highlighted as essential for creating a conducive setting that promotes focused and effective intervention sessions. Overall, the participant's observations underscore the critical role of minimizing distractions like noise and heat in facilitating successful interventions and achieving positive results.

Theme 4: The Enhancement

According to Bulig and Bacatan (2023), improving peer tutoring interventions with extended implementation aims to optimize students' reading comprehension benefits. This may entail prolonging sessions from a few occurrences to weeks or even months to facilitate more profound learning. Furthermore, enhancing training may involve incorporating particular tactics to enhance comprehension, critical thinking, and a passion for reading. By customizing the intervention for specific age groups, such as an elementary school where it proves highly effective, and extending the duration, a comprehensive intervention is crafted with a lasting influence on students' reading progress.

The Teacher said that:

"I suggest to give more focus specifically in peer tutoring which it gives better impact to the child's comprehension and ability to read. Aside from that, it should be taught for longer periods like weeks or months."

For students in elementary school, peer tutoring is a highly effective strategy for improving children's reading comprehension and ability, boosting confidence, developing critical thinking skills, and fostering a love of learning. When implemented in a well-structured program that extends over several weeks or months, peer tutoring can have a significant impact. This approach warrants further investigation and wider implementation in schools.

Conclusions

Utilizing PQ4R and annotations to improve students' reading comprehension is empirically effective. However, in this study, this instructional tool was applied to Grade 6 pupils, yet it showed a statistically insignificant difference. The result indicated minimal progress, failing to reach the 0.05 level of significance. Nevertheless, the numerical analysis suggests that integrating this instructional tool yielded a modest improvement compared to the control group, indicating a tangible benefit over the class that did not undergo the intervention. The qualitative insights from the study underscore the importance of PQ4R and annotations in enhancing students' reading comprehension efficiency. Thus, there are observable factors such as intrinsic and extrinsic distractions that may have influenced the numerical results. Meanwhile, further research and refinement of instructional methods may be necessary to enhance the effectiveness of this approach.

The reading intervention was not effective during utilization. For starters, the students were having a hard time reading some words, especially those that were difficult and new to them. They would often stumble while reading some words. In addition, their attention span was short, and they were easily distracted by the noises, which is one of the factors that affected the PQ4R intervention. To optimize reading comprehension, it is advisable to select a quiet environment—such as a library or a cozy corner at home—where distractions are minimized. In this serene setting, the mind can fully engage with the story, allowing thoughts to connect without interruption. Additionally, the presentation of the stories and difficult words should be creative and eye-catching. There should be an activity or games connected to the text or story and utilization of PQ4R strategies. Moreover, there is a need to sustain the implementation of PQ4R and Annotation strategies for an extended duration. Peer teaching should be emphasized to address the diverse learning paces of students, as some may grasp the material at different speeds, particularly in comprehension. It is essential to acknowledge that students can easily get distracted, especially by hunger and hot weather. These can affect their focus and ability to

learn effectively.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Mary Grace M. Mahusay

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

BB. Rose O. Aguilon

Cebu Technological University - Philippines

Nino T. Baga

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Mariz Bahenting

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Cherry Lou L. Calabroso

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Melody A. Canoy

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Jeziel A. Dionaldo

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Lezel Gabunada

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Jan Michelle Guimaras

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Khym Yvette A. Javierto

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Jemelyn L. Morales

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Kin Louie M. Patiluna

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Marichie T. Sadagnet

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Kyla Janin D. Sevilla

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Laarnie Blessful M. Sucal

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Joan Marie P. Tagyamon

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Cyril A. Cabello PhD(c)

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Vicente S. Erojo

Tuble Elementary School

Department of Education – Philippines

Sulpicio D. Bani Jr.

Tuble Elementary School

Department of Education – Philippines

Ana Marie R. Schauf

Tuble Elementary School

Department of Education – Philippines